

ANALYSIS OF WORKS AIMED AT CLEANING SUBMERSIBLE EQUIPMENT

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Abstract

The article discusses the causes and classification of the causes of the destruction of the collector and the removal of sand. During the operation of wells complicated by the removal of mechanical impurities, there is a problem of clogging of the bottom of wells, equipment and the bottom-hole zone of the formation, which leads to a decrease in the potential of the well in terms of fluid extraction volumes. A similar situation occurs during technological operations.

The occurrence of sand or paraffin-hydrate "plugs" for oil and gas companies is quite common. In relation to underground pumping equipment, mechanical impurities are the main cause of breakdowns and the formation of structural defects. According to well-known statistics, the percentage of pump equipment breakdowns associated with exposure to mechanical impurities far exceeds the influence of other geological and technical factors, the main of which are corrosion and salt formation. For most oil fields in Western and Eastern Siberia, mechanical impurities account for 35-50% of the total number of the main causes of failures of deep pumps, while corrosion is 20-25%, and salt formation is 15-20%. Also, due to the removal of sand, sand plugs are formed, which cover the entire interval of the perforation of the well, as a result of which the well ceases to function due to the lack of fluid inflow from the reservoir.

Keywords: Borehole, bottom-hole zone, reservoir, electric central pump, hydraulic fracturing, geological and technical measures.

To maintain the level of oil production, it is sometimes advisable to increase the flow rates of wells, which inevitably leads to high filtration rates that contribute to the disruption and removal of mechanical impurities from weakly cemented reservoirs of the bottomhole zone due to the destruction of the collector skeleton. In this case, the process of destruction of the reservoir will be continuous due to the constant removal of particles of destroyed rock into the well.

As a result of all the above, the problems of eliminating sand jams in producing wells are global in nature.

The most important scientific and technical problem of field development is the simultaneous provision of high levels and rates of production of hydrocarbon raw materials with the most complete extraction of it from the subsoil with high technical and economic performance of oil and gas producing enterprises. One of the reasons that does not allow to solve this problem effectively is the sand occurrence and removal of mechanical impurities during the operation of wells.

If until recently this problem was very relevant for the fields of Azerbaijan, Krasnodar Krai, etc., now a number of its aspects need to be solved in the conditions of the fields of Western and Eastern Siberia. So, for example, at the large fields of Samotlor, Vankor and a number of other fields, there has been a steady trend of an annual increase in failures of electric centrifugal pumps due to the high content of mechanical impurities in the production of wells.

Many research papers and articles have been devoted to the problems of cleaning downhole equipment. This problem is relevant for the oil and gas industry. A large number of scientific works are aimed at preventing sand occurrence, salt deposits and ASF, as well as the elimination of these complications during well operation. The currently existing methods of combating

mechanical impurities have a number of significant drawbacks, which in the real economic conditions of the development of oil fields (especially fields at a late stage of development) limits the possibility of their use.

The solution of the problem in this area of oil production is being held back due to the lack of inexpensive, highly effective means of protecting the ESP from mechanical impurities contained in the well products.

Let's consider the goals, conclusions and recommendations of some works devoted to this problem.

In the work [1] "Improvement of oil production technology in conditions of intensive removal of mechanical impurities", the author, using the example of the Samotlorskoye field, describes methods of working with submersible pumping equipment (ESP) in conditions of high removal of mechanical impurities.

The purpose of the study in this work is to increase the efficiency of the operation of wells equipped with ESP for the extraction of liquids with a high concentration of suspended particles.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set and solved:

- the peculiarities of the influence of mechanical impurities on the operation of downhole equipment are revealed;

- the analysis of the current state of existing scientific and technical solutions for the protection of downhole equipment from mechanical impurities was carried out and their classification was developed;

- technical means have been developed to protect the ESP from mechanical impurities;

- technical means of protection of the ESP during the extraction of liquids with a high concentration of suspended particles have been tested in field conditions. Their effectiveness was evaluated.

The scientific novelty of this work consists in obtaining analytical dependencies between the content of

mechanical impurities in the production of wells operating the AB11-2 formation of the Samotlorskoye field and the technological mode of their operation. A classification of methods for protecting downhole equipment from mechanical impurities has been developed. A method of protection is proposed and scientifically substantiated

ESP using standing waves artificially generated in the flow of the extracted borehole fluid.

The practical significance of the results obtained in this work is clearly expressed. The developed methods of protection of downhole equipment from mechanical impurities allowed:

- to increase the operating time for failure of SHGN by an average of 3 times using a gas-sand separator (RF Patent No. 2212533);
- reduce the cost of cleaning the downhole zone of the formation by reducing the flow rate of the working fluid by 2 times when using a hydraulic pulse generator (RF Patent No. 2160351);
- reduce vibration in the well by 6.2 times by reducing the pulsation of the gas-liquid mixture;
- reduce the concentration of suspended particles (EHF) in the production of the well by an average of 3.4 times. In the stationary mode of operation, the decrease in EHF was 1.9 times.

The developed technical means of protecting the downhole equipment from mechanical impurities have passed field tests at the wells of the Samotlorskoye field.

The technical and economic efficiency of their use in flight-hazardous wells and wells with a high content of mechanical impurities will be expressed in an increase in the time to failure, which will primarily affect the efficiency of oil field development by reducing operating costs, and consequently reducing the cost of oil production.

This work has the following main conclusions and recommendations:

1. As a result of the analysis of geological and field data of the Samotlor deposit, a number of features of the influence of mechanical impurities on the operation

- of downhole equipment were revealed. It is shown that:
 - ECN accidents in 37% of cases occurred due to vibration. According to the results of the investigation of the causes of accidents, it was found that in 74% of cases the occurrence of increased vibration is associated with a significant content of mechanical impurities in the production of wells, as evidenced by the strong abrasive wear of the working bodies of pumps;
 - 39% of wells located in the frequently repaired ESP fund have failed due to the high content of mechanical impurities in the extracted liquid;
 - the main reasons for the failure of the ECP after hydraulic fracturing are the removal of proppant (23% of cases) and sand (20% of cases).

2. The influence of the technological mode of operation of the wells of the AB11-2 formation of the Samotlor deposit on the content of mechanical impurities in their products was confirmed in the following dependencies:

- the dependence of the content of mechanical impurities on the water content of well products – $R_2=0.78$ for reservoirs characterized by a complex geophysical index $\text{aps} < 0.5$ and $R_2=0.54$ for reservoirs with $\text{aps} > 0.5$;

- the dependence of the content of mechanical impurities on the depression on the formation, as well as the dependence of the content of mechanical impurities on the ratio of bottom-hole pressure to

- reservoir pressure - $R_2 = 0.5$;

- dependence of the content of mechanical impurities on the productivity coefficient of wells – $R_2 = 0.43$.

3. The paper proposes a classification of methods for protecting downhole pumping equipment from mechanical impurities. The currently existing methods of protecting downhole pumping equipment from mechanical impurities are divided into four groups: chemical, technical, technological and preventive.

4. Based on theoretical research, as well as analysis of domestic and foreign experience in protecting downhole equipment from mechanical impurities, a gas-mixing separator for SHGN has been developed, as a result of the introduction of which the operating time for failure of SHGN has been increased by 3 times.

5. Based on the phenomenon of coagulation of particles suspended in a liquid, a device has been developed to protect the ECN from mechanical impurities (acoustic noise converter – APSH), which converts the low-frequency vibration of an electric centrifugal pump into a frequency range favorable for particle coagulation.

6. The obtained test results of acoustic noise converters allow us to recommend their implementation in flight-hazardous wells and wells with a high content of mechanical impurities. The projected value of the annual economic effect that can be obtained by reducing vibration and EHF from the introduction of acoustic noise converters is 3.9 million rubles per year for 1 well [2].

- The work [3] is devoted to "Improving the efficiency of fastening the bottom-hole zone of the formation in order to reduce sand occurrence."

- The purpose of this work is to develop a model of the state of the bottom-hole zone of the formation, taking into account the deformation and spatial instability of weakly cemented sandstone to solve practical problems of reducing and preventing sand occurrences.

- The research tasks solved in this paper to achieve this goal, the author sets the following:

- investigation of the causes of sand manifestations;

- study of the relationship of methods of fire protection with the properties of reservoir rocks;

- development of a method for modeling a weakly cemented collector in order to clarify the limits of its strength stability under operating conditions;

- establishing relationships to determine the critical state (moment of destruction) of the skeleton of weakly cemented sandstone;

- determination of the criterion of applicability of the method of chemical action for fixing weakly cemented sandstone.

The scientific novelty of the obtained results is as follows:

1. A model of the state of the bottom-hole zone of the formation has been developed, taking into account the deformation-spatial instability of weakly cemented sandstone.

2. The criteria for determining the critical state (moment of destruction) of the skeleton of weakly cemented sandstone are selected.

3. The criterion of applicability of the method of chemical action for fixing the bottom-hole zone of the formation is determined.

The practical significance and implementation of the results of the work [4] consists in:

- the use of methods for determining the forecast parameters of the onset of the critical state of reservoir rocks in the bottom-hole zone of the formation;

- implementation of technological principles for increasing the efficiency of fastening the bottom-hole zone of the formation by controlling the processes of sand formation;

- development of a method for selecting a technological solution for fixing the bottom-hole zone of the formation, taking into account the state of rocks.

Summing up this scientific work, special attention should be paid to the conclusions that the author gives in his work:

1. The principles of variable completion technology have been developed, with the help of which it becomes possible to optimize the composition of completion management methods and make them more flexible and effective.

2. The analysis of the characteristics of the state and traditional methods of limiting sand occurrences in a number of deposits of the Krasnodar Territory is carried out.

3. Principles and analytical expressions have been developed to determine the forecast parameters of the onset of the critical state of reservoir rocks in the bottom-hole zone of the formation using a statistical dynamic model of deformation-spatial instability.

4. The strengths of homogeneous and heterogeneous sandstone structures have been experimentally investigated.

5. Classification of rocks according to the degree of heterogeneity has been developed.

6. Criteria for the expediency of using methods of chemical reinforcement of rocks have been developed [5-7].

Conclusions Experiments and observations carried out at various oil and gas facilities allowed us to conclude that none of the methods of restoring productivity (chemical, hydromechanical or combined) do not return wells to their original flow rates during operation, but are temporary. In this regard, it is important to use such a system in which frequent shutdowns of the well are combined with a constant cyclic alternation of hydromechanical and chemical cleaning methods. A possible solution to the problem of organizing the continuous cyclic operation of the cleaning equipment is associated with the automation of its operation without carrying out lifting operations.

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